

Figure S2

Figure S2. Sample DatLab tracings of JO_2 and JH_2O_2 during chamber O_2 depletion. Representative DatLab tracings of the raw JO_2 (top row of panels) and JH_2O_2 (bottom panels) signals from cardiac mitochondrial preparations including chamber oxygen content (blue line, left y-axes) and the uncorrected JO_2 signal (red line, right y-axes) with corresponding recordings of cumulative chamber fluorescence (black line, left y-axis; raw fluorescence units, RFU) and rate of chamber fluorescence development (green line, right y-axis; slope of black line) from the same experiment over time as chamber O_2 is depleted*. Results show that mitochondria maintain stable JO_2 down to essentially 0 μM O_2 , while homogenate and particularly permeabilized fibers begin to decline exponentially below ~ 20 - 40 μM O_2 , illustrating the variations in O_2 diffusion limitation of JO_2 across these preparations. The JH_2O_2 fluorescence signal declines linearly with chamber $[O_2]$ in all sample preparations down to near anoxic conditions, then decreases further to just above zero in anoxia, illustrating the high O_2 -dependence of mtROS production and chemical background fluorescence (further illustrated in Figure S3 below).

*Note that the red and green lines are time integrals (averages) of change in the raw O_2 (blue) and fluorescence (green) signals, respectively, so do not immediately respond to the onset of anoxia.

Figure S3

Figure S3. Contribution of chemical background to the total rate of fluorescence development by mitochondrial preparations across different chamber O₂ concentrations. A) Total (uncorrected) rates of resorufin fluorescence developed by mitochondrial preparations and chemical background (without sample) as chamber [O₂] declines from 400 μM to anoxia. Results illustrate the linear dependence of mitochondrial $\dot{J}H_2O_2$ and chemical background rate on chamber [O₂], and extremely low sample and background flux signals in anoxia (inset). **B)** Contribution of chemical background fluorescence to total rate of fluorescence developed by mitochondrial preparations as chamber [O₂] declines. Results illustrate that chemical background flux contributes to ~34-93% of total rate of fluorescence developed by biological samples, depending on mitochondrial preparation, tissue and chamber [O₂]. In general, the contribution of chemical background to total flux increases as chamber [O₂] declines, reflecting a greater O₂-dependence of sample (mitochondrial) $\dot{J}H_2O_2$ than the chemical background reactions between AmR and media components. Contributions of background to fluorescence flux in anoxia (inset) were highly variable given the extremely low signal intensity, but may reflect differences in the composition of the mitochondrial preparations and/or their interaction with buffer components.

Figure S4

Figure S4. Representative O₂ and fluorescence tracings from each of the six mitochondrial preparations. For clarity, a sample experiment in heart mitochondria (top left) illustrates the change in chamber oxygen content (blue line, left y-axes) and the uncorrected JO_2 signal (red line, right y-axes) with corresponding recordings of cumulative chamber fluorescence (black line, left y-axis; raw fluorescence units, RFU) and rate of chamber fluorescence development (green line, right y-axis) during the transition from the LEAK state supported by malate, pyruvate, glutamate and succinate (MPGS) to the OXPHOS state (induced by the addition of ADP) at room air saturated [O₂]_s. Data from experiments in Figures 2 and 3 of the main manuscript are illustrated in the subsequent panel, which were collected between 350-400 μ M O₂ for consistency across all mitochondrial preparations. This required reoxygenation of the chamber between the LEAK and OXPHOS states at least once during the experiment (shaded portions of the remaining panels) to obtain stable flux recordings in both respiratory states. Only chamber O₂ content and fluorescence tracing are presented from these experiments for clarity, given wide variations in the flux tracings induced by the reoxygenation procedure.

Supplemental References

1. **Komlodi T, Sobotka O, Krumschnabel G, Bezuidenhout N, Hiller E, Doerrier C, and Gnaiger E.** Comparison of Mitochondrial Incubation Media for Measurement of Respiration and Hydrogen Peroxide Production. *Methods Mol Biol* 1782: 137-155, 2018.
2. **Krumschnabel G, Fontana-Ayoub M, Sumbalova Z, Heidler J, Gauper K, Fasching M, and Gnaiger E.** Simultaneous high-resolution measurement of mitochondrial respiration and hydrogen peroxide production. *Methods Mol Biol* 1264: 245-261, 2015.